

Recommendation 22:

Using 'Smart Workplace' to meet the business need 'Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures'

Status quo:

According to a CBRE foresight study in 2040 e.g. the following properties will characterize a smart workplace:

- Flexible working contracts (increase mobility and unconventional working patterns)
- 'wellness' services at the workplace
- Focus on collaboration

Many employees prefer to have a mobile working environment and mobile solutions to help them to improve their work-life-balance. Thus many mobile solutions (like smartphones & tablets, wearables, cloud computing) would help to attract new talents.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

There are already a lot of technologies available to enhance the work-live-balance:

- Mobile working environments
- Mobile solutions: smartphones and tablets, wearables, cloud computing
- Communication platforms
- Time accounts
- as well as various recruiting activities in Social Media

Non-technical challenges:

- *Strategies for acquisition and retention and training possibilities* should be developed. Stakeholders have to be aware of the future risks. A flexible smart workplace is a great possibility to acquire and retain employees that lead a family life.
- *A flexible smart workplace* additionally strengthen globalization processes while enables collaboration with partners in different time zones. So business can grow fast, and enable high-powered freelancers to emerge.
- When dealing with flexible smart workplaces the 24/7 work culture have to be covered by *regulations or a legal framework*. Otherwise health issues, like psychological disease, can be the result.

Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures:

This need pertains to recruiting talented employees and skilled staff, and retaining them by providing talent enhancement programs. The specific sub needs that emerged through our desk research are: attract skilled workers, STEM-skilled (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) workforce and enhance talent of existing employees . Our informant mentioned, " Stop brain drain of young talents."

Smart Workplace:

*A Smart or High Performance Workplace is a physical or virtual environment designed to make workers as effective as possible in supporting business goals and providing value. Such a workplace results from continually balancing investment in people, process, physical environment and technology, to measurably enhance the ability of workers to learn, discover, innovate, team and lead, and to achieve efficiency and financial benefit.**

*Gartner IT Glossary, High Performance Workplace, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/high-performance-workplace>
TechRepublic, Gartner Hype Cycle: Exploring the leading-edge technologies for a digital business,
<http://www.techrepublic.com/article/gartner-hype-cycle-exploring-the-leading-edge-technologies-for-a-digital-business/>